

Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in Concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State. The study adopted pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Physics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Kagarko local government area of Kaduna state. A sample size of 86 (49 Male and 37 Female) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The experimental group were exposed to Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy while the Control group were taught using Conventional Method. Two instruments, namely Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Physics Attitude Scale (PAS) were used for data collection and had reliability coefficient of 0.82 and 0.74 obtained by the used of Kuder-Richardson 21 (K-R 21) and Cronbach Alpha (α) respectively. Two research questions were raised with four corresponding hypotheses. These hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the use of Activity-Based Strategy in teaching physics concept to secondary school students enhanced students' achievement and attitude. The study also revealed that there was no significant interaction between gender and instructional approach on students' achievement and attitude. The study concluded that the application of Activity-Based Strategy improved students' achievement and increased positive attitude toward Physics. The study recommended the provision of in-service training and retraining for teachers on the use of Activity-Based Strategy for teaching Physics.

Keywords: Activity-Based Strategy, Achievement, Attitude, Student

Introduction

Science is the foundation upon which the bulk of present-day technological breakthrough is built. All over the world, nations are striving hard to develop technologically and scientifically, since the world is turning scientific and all the proper functioning of lives depend greatly on science (Oluwasegun, Ohwofosirai & Emagbetere, 2015). Series of attempts and innovations have been made to recognize science and technology at various levels of the Nigerian education system by the government, educational institutions, scientific agencies, and professional association (Ojelade, 2010).

Physics is one of the subjects in science education. It involves the study of matter, energy, and their interactions. Any nation that pays lip service to the development of Physics education will surely lag behind among the community of nations. It is because of this that African countries must find ways of improving their Physics education program at the secondary and post-secondary school levels (Benson, 2017).

Physics plays a major role in health education, economic development, energy, and the environment. The X-rays, radioisotope nuclear resource imaging, laser electron, microscope, and synchrotron radiator among other advances in medicine depend on Physics-based technology (Kola, 2013). Our world is more connected through technology and the conduction of business around the world is done almost effortlessly (Bello, 2012).

Despite the importance of Physics in scientific and technological development, it appears as though Physics education has been facing various challenges. First, the enrolment in Physics courses at all levels is low in many African countries (Amunga, Musasia & Musera, 2011). Many reasons are advanced for this discrepancy which include inadequate lower level preparations,

weak mathematics background, lack of job opportunities outside the teaching profession, inadequate teacher qualification as well as possession of below standard pedagogical content knowledge (Semela, 2010).

The research reports on the effects of laboratory equipment indicated a significant difference between the performance of Biology Students exposed to adequately equipped laboratories and those exposed to the inadequately equipped laboratory. The difference was in favour of those exposed to the adequately equipped laboratory (Katcha & Wushishi, 2015). Intensive practical activities have a positive influence on students' achievements in Physics. It improves Physics academic performance of the learner (Amadalo, Alhayo & Thomas, 2016).

According to Muchai (2016), studies on the effects of practical work on students' achievements in Physics, showed that a practical approach resulted in higher students' achievements in Physics, lead to improved students' attitude toward Physics, and also, increased higher students' enrolment in Physics at the Kenya Certificate of Secondary School Education. Shittu (2013), further stated that students who were taught light concepts using a guided inquiry strategy achieved significantly higher than those taught the same light concepts using the lecture method.

Nwayiabai's (2014), study revealed that the use of Origami in teaching enhanced students' achievement, interest, and retention in geometry. Also, it had no statistically differential effect on male and female students' achievements, interests, and retention. Furthermore, there was a significant interaction effect between gender and instructional material on retention of the concepts taught.

It is important to realize that a positive student attitude towards the content of an instructional activity should be a critical goal for the teacher because there is a positive correlation between student attitude and student achievement (Dajal, Ogar & Sunday, 2019). Teaching strategies can influence the attitude of students positively or negatively, this suggests that the attitude of students plays a significant part in any satisfactory explanation of the variable level of performance by students in their school science subject (Shittu, 2013).

Studies by Dawaki (2012), point out that most science teachers use the traditional method. These methods do not allow active students' participation in science lessons rather, students memorize, and regurgitate facts and concepts without the basic understanding of what it is they have memorized. Teachers serve as pipelines and seek to transfer their thoughts and meanings to the passive students. For this reason, the "Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State" towards learning in Physics are studied.

The teaching and learning of Physics in most classrooms face a lot of problems. Most of the teachers use the Conventional Teaching Method that comprises Talk and Chalk, Note taking and Memorization. They do not make use of Activity-Based Strategies, where the learners play an active role in the learning process. This inability of the Physics teachers in the use of Activity-Based Strategies might be the cause of poor performance in the subject at both teacher's made examinations and external examinations. Thus, this study is aimed at comparing the mean performance of students taught Physics using the Activity-Based Strategy and Conventional Method in order to determine which one is more effective in teaching Physics in Senior Secondary Schools in Kagarko Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

The main objectives of this study was to determine the Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State. The specific objectives are to;

1. Determine the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
2. Determine the mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

Research Questions

This following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference in achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using the Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?
2. What is the mean difference in attitude rating scores between students taught physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H0₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
2. **H0₂**: There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
3. **H0₃**: There is no significant difference in mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
4. **H0₄**: There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

Methodology

The study adopted pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Physics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Kagarko local government area of Kaduna state. A sample size of 86 (49 male and 37 female) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The experimental group were exposed to Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy while the Control group were taught using Conventional Method. Two instruments, namely Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Physics Attitude Scale (PAS) were used for data collection and had reliability coefficient of 0.82 and 0.74 obtained by used of Kuder-Richardson 21 (K-R 21) and Cronbach Alpha (α) respectively.

Data Collection Procedure.

After permission was sought and granted by the school authorities in order to use their schools for the study. Thereafter, PAT and PAS were served to 86 SSSII Physics students from the selected schools. The results were then used to ascertain relative ability in achievement in Physics concepts.

The Physics students of the intact classes of the two groups were taught using the Activity-Based Strategy for the experimental group, while the Conventional teaching Method was used for the control group. The same topics were taught in both schools (groups) using an intact class

The post-test of PAT and PAS was administered to Physics students at the end of the 8th week of the study. The students of the two (2) groups; the experimental group and the control group took the post-test.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the study were analyzed using frequency count, mean score, and standard deviation to answer research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic at 0.05 level of significance was used to analyze data for testing the null hypotheses. the analysis was computer-based, with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using the Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Experimental and Control Groups in Pre-test and Post-test (PAT)

Group		Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Gain
Experimental	Mean	25.80	43.70	17.90
	Std. Deviation	0.91	0.83	
	N	45	45	
Control	Mean	25.90	27.50	1.60
	Std. Deviation	0.86	0.86	

	N	41	41	
Mean difference				16.30

The results in table 1 show that the mean achievement score of Pre-PAT for the experimental group was 25.80 with a standard deviation of 0.91, while that of the control group was 25.90 with a standard deviation of 0.86. At the beginning of the study, the subjects were almost at the same level in their knowledge of Physics. The mean achievement score of Post-PAT for the experimental group was observed to be 43.70 with a standard deviation of 0.83 while that of the control group, the mean achievement score of Post-PAT was 27.50 with a standard deviation of 0.86. The result showed that the use of Activity-Based Strategy had a positive effect on students' achievement in Physics in the experimental group than those in the control group. The difference in the mean gain between the two groups is 16.30 in favor of the experimental group.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in attitude rating scores between students taught physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation on Attitude of Experimental and Control Groups in Pre-test and Post-test (PAS)

Group		Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Gain
Experimental	Mean	1.60	3.42	1.82
	Std. Deviation	0.26	0.41	
	N	45	45	
Control	Mean	1.56	2.05	0.49
	Std. Deviation	0.31	0.39	
	N	41	41	
Mean difference				1.33

From table 2, it could be observed that the mean Pre-PAS of the experimental group is 1.60 with a standard deviation of 0.26 and that of the control group 1.56 with a standard deviation of 0.31. At the beginning of the study, the subjects were almost at the same level in their attitude toward Physics. The table also shows that the experimental group of Post-PAS is 3.42 with a standard deviation of 0.41 while that of the control group is 2.05 with a standard deviation of 0.39. The difference in the mean gain attitude scores of the two groups is 1.33 in favor of the experimental group.

Hypotheses

H₀:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area. To test for hypothesis; 1 and 2, ANCOVA statistic was used and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ANCOVA Results of the Experimental and Control Groups on PAT Due to Method and Gender (for hypotheses 1 and 2)

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean	F	Sig
Corrected model	5716.242	4	1429.061	47.581	0.000
Intercept	6416.382	1	6416.382	213.635	0.000
Pre-test	18.811	1	18.811	0.626	0.431
Group (Method)	5538.809	1	5538.809	184.416	0.000*
Gender (Sex)	88.910	1	88.910	2.960	0.089**
Group * Gender	1.788	1	1.788	0.060	0.808**
Error	2432.781	81	30.034		
Total	118456.000	86			
Corrected total	8149.023	85			

* = Significant at 0.05 level of probability

** = Not significant

Table 3, indicates that the value of the significance of F on achievement is 0.000 as against the already set alpha level of 0.05 at 1 and 81 df (degrees of freedom). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant achievement scores is rejected. This implies that the experimental groups achieved significantly higher than the control group in the SSS II Physics concepts taught using Activity-Based Strategy.

H0₂:

There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

The result of table 3, also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender as measured by the Physics achievement scores of Post-PAT. The value of the significance of F of the 2-way interaction (Method * Gender) is 0.808 as against 0.05 level of significance already set prior to the experiment. Since the significance of F value is greater than the already set alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This means that the interaction effect between method and gender as measured by their mean Physics achievement test scores is not statistically significant.

H0₃:

There is no significant difference in mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area. To test the hypothesis; 3 and 4, ANCOVA statistic was used and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results of the Experimental and Control Groups on PAS Due to Gender; Treatment and Interaction (for hypotheses 3 and 4)

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean	F	Sig
Corrected model	41.173 ^a	4	10.293	41.325	0.000
Intercept	64.575	1	64.575	259.251	0.000
Pre-test	0.224	1	0.224	0.898	0.346
Group (method)	240.063	1	40.063	160.843	0.000*
Gender (Sex)	0.540	1	0.540	2.168	0.145**
Group*Gender	0.021	1	0.021	0.084	0.773**
Error	20.176	81	0.249		
Total	720.000	86			
Corrected total	61.349	85			

* = Significant at .05 level of probability

**= No significant.

The result of table 4, shows that there is a significant difference in the mean score attitude between the students taught with Activity-Based Strategy and those taught with Traditional Method at 0.05 level of significance. The value of significance of F on attitude is 0.000 as against the already set of 0.05 at 1 and 81 df (degrees of freedom). Based on this, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. The implication of this is that students that were taught using the Activity-Based Strategy gained more positive attitude in Physics than those in the Traditional Method.

H0₄:

There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area. Table 4, also revealed that gender does not influence the treatment as regards attitude. The value of F of the 2-way interaction (Method * Gender) is 0.773 as against 0.05 level of significance. Since the significance of F value is greater than the already set alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. This means that there is no statistically significant attitude between treatment and gender in students' attitudes toward Physics.

Discussion of Findings

In table 1 the mean achievement scores of the experimental group in Post-PAT is higher than the Post-PAT mean achievement scores of the control group. This indicated that the use of Activity-Based Strategy concepts improved students' achievement in Physics. The result was further confirmed by the result in table 3, which revealed that the method was a significant factor in students' achievement in Physics. Hence, students who were taught Physics using an Activity-Based

Strategy achieved higher than those taught using the Traditional Method. The implication of this is that the instructional material used in teaching Physics can produce differential effects on students with respect to Physics achievement. This positive and higher achievement may have been a result of the active participation of the students due to the fact that the approach used was practical in nature and therefore ensured students' activity. This finding agrees with Katcha and Wushishi (2015), Odutuyi (2015), Amadalo, Aphyayo and Thomas (2016), and Muchai (2016), who in their studies found that adequately equipped laboratory, practical work, and practical instructional approach enhanced students' achievement. These findings also lend support to other researchers such as Shittu (2013) and Nwanyiabai (2014), who found that students exposed to Activity-Based instruction methods such as guided inquiring strategy and Origami performed better than their counterparts exposed to the traditional method.

The result in table 2, revealed that the mean attitude rating of the students in the experimental group was almost the same as the mean attitude rating of those in the control group at Pre-PAS. But at Post-PAS, the mean attitude rating of the students in the experimental group is significantly higher than those of the control group. This is further confirmed by the ANCOVA result in table 4, which indicates that the experimental group recorded a significantly higher attitude rating than the control group. These findings confirm that the use of the Activity-Based Strategy concept enhances students' attitude toward Physics. The result of this study is also in accordance with other studies such as Shittu (2011), Nwanyiabai (2014), and Muchai (2016) which confirmed that the use of appropriate instructional material enhances students' interest and attitude in learning Physics. The approach motivated and sustained their attitude thereby evoking a greater understanding of Physics.

The result of table 3, the analysis of the covariance test of interaction revealed that the significance of F is 0.808 for the 2-way-interaction, as against the already set alpha significant level of 0.05. It was found that there is no significant interaction between instructional material and gender on students' achievement in Physics concepts taught during the study. The findings of this study are in agreement with Nwanyiabai (2014) who found no significant interaction effect of instructional model and gender on students' achievement.

Similarly, from table 4, the result of the analysis of the covariance test of interaction showed that, for the 2-way-interaction, the significance of F value is 0.773. Since this is greater than the significance level already set at 0.05, the conclusion is that there is no significant interaction between instructional material and gender on students' attitudes. These findings imply that achievement and interest for male and female students are consistent. The result of this finding is also in compliance with Nwanyiabai (2014) who found no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies and gender on students' attitudes.

Conclusion

Based on the result obtained, the researcher draws the following conclusion:

1. The use of Activity-Based Strategy as an instructional approach enhanced students' achievement in Physics better than the conventional instructional approach.
2. Similarly, the use of Activity-Based Strategy proved superior to the conventional method in promoting students' attitudes and achievement in Physics concepts.
3. There was no significant interaction between Treatment and gender in achievement and attitude in Physics among secondary school students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this research:

1. Curriculum planners in Secondary Schools should include Activity-Based Strategy as one of the necessary instructional materials for the teaching of Physics;
2. Government and curriculum planners should incorporate Activity-Based Strategy into the curricula of education faculties in universities and teacher training colleges, to ensure proper training of teachers in the new concept;
3. Government/education administrators should also organize public lectures, seminars, and workshops incorporating of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) on Activity-Based Strategy in schools, as a way of marketing the new concept;
4. Government should through appropriate agencies, sponsor further research into the possible application of Activity-Based Strategy in other aspects of science and technology with Numeral Not bullet or point).

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